

Research Article

Exploiting Negative Sample Selection for Prioritizing Candidate Disease Genes

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ABSTRACT

A major challenge in bio-medicine is finding the genetic causes of human diseases, and researchers are often faced with a large number of candidate genes. Gene prioritization methods provide a valuable support in guiding researchers to detect reliable candidate causative-genes for a disease under study. Indeed, such methods rank genes according to their association with a disease of interest. Actually, the majority of genetic disorders has few or none causative genes associated with them; this induces a high labeling unbalance in the corresponding ranking problems, thus linking the need of achieving reliable solutions to the adoption of imbalance-aware techniques. We propose the use of an expressly designed imbalance-aware methodology for prioritizing genes, which first rebalances the training set entries through a negative selection procedure, then applies a learning algorithm 'sensitive' to the misclassification of positive instances, to provide the gene ranking. The algorithm has a reduced time complexity, which makes feasible its application on large-sized datasets. The validation of this methodology proved its competitiveness with state-of-art techniques on a benchmark composed of 708 selected Medical Subject Headings diseases, and provided some putative novel gene-disease associations.

KEYWORDS

disease-gene prioritization; graph-based node ranking; cost-sensitive learning; negative selection

AVAILABILITY AND REQUIREMENTS

Benchmark data are downloadable from the Web site mentioned in [1]; data produced in this paper are available at <http://frasca.di.unimi.it/data/GP/>.

INTRODUCTION

The discovery of so-called *disease genes*, whose disruption causes congenital or acquired diseases, is important both towards diagnosis and new therapies, through the elucidation of diseases etiology. Current high-throughput sequencing methods used for disease gene discovery can generate very large volumes of data, by identifying a high number of non-synonymous genetic

variants [2]. The regions identified, however, often contain tens to hundreds of candidate genes. Finding the causal gene(s) among these candidates is then an expensive and time-consuming process, which requires extensive laboratory experiments [3]. This list of genes is very large, thus it can be just partially handled by manual curators. Computational methods can drastically reduce the set of candidate genes. Indeed, several strategies have emerged to rank the variants and the genes that they affect, with those most likely to cause disease ranked highest, through a process termed *gene prioritization* (GP) [4]. This task is extremely challenging since complex genetic disorders often involve several primarily responsible genes; indeed, in most cases there has been only limited success in identifying causative genes.

First high-throughput efforts investigated gene-disease associations based on *gene expression profiles* or *genome wide association studies* (GWAS), which identify genes involved in human diseases by searching the genome for small variations, called *single nucleotide polymorphisms* (SNPs), occurring more frequently in patients with a particular disease than in healthy people [5].

Attempts based on whole exome sequencing (WES) have been proposed, which aim at capturing all exonic and flanking sequences and may also include probes to target microRNA and other sequences of interest [6], and which have reported a successful molecular diagnosis in up to 25% of cases in large cohorts of unselected, consecutive patients [7]. More recently, phenotype-driven analysis of exome data have also been investigated with the aim of filtering out common variants and those deemed to be non-pathogenic [8]. Fewer approaches attempted to apply tissue-specific expression patterns based on the hypothesis that genes responsible for a tissue(s)-specific phenotype are expected to be more highly expressed in affected than unaffected tissues [9]. Other relevant approaches focus on the analysis of knowledge-driven multi-SNP modelling [10], local clustering on gene association networks [11], text-mining [12, 13] and disease phenotypes analysis [14].

For its intuitive interpretation, many other works on gene prioritization have exploited the *guilt-by-association* (GBA) rule, in which candidate disease genes are ranked assuming that similar genes tend to be involved in similar diseases [15]. These methods

are based on gene networks, where nodes represent genes and connections encode precomputed functional relationships among genes, derived from functional annotations, transcriptional co-expression regulation, direct molecular interactions, and others [16]. By exploiting the topology of the network and the prior information encoded in the set of known causative genes for the disease under study, many approaches have been adopted to compute gene rankings, ranging from protein-protein interaction network analysis and semi-supervised graph partitioning [16], to flow propagation [17], and random walks [18]. Finally, recent studies have improved the GP performance by integrating multiple data sources, including expression profiles, SNP genotype data, expression quantitative trait loci, and so on [19]: network-based approaches indeed construct a consensus network which includes the specificity of each network, covers more genes and contains more accurate pairwise connections [20].

Despite the benefits and the effectiveness of the above-mentioned studies, they usually do not take into account the imbalance in GP data: just few causative genes (the positive instances of the problem) are available for the majority of human diseases (see for instance the Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man (OMIM) database [21]). Machine learning algorithms, not specifically handling data imbalance, usually suffer from a strong decay in performance, since they tend to learn mainly the majority class while ignoring or misclassifying minority class samples [22]. In our context, this is a critical point, since the minority class carries almost all the information we have about the disease under study. Hence disease-gene prioritization requires the adoption of specifically designed imbalance-aware machine learning techniques, often referred as *cost-sensitive* [22]. Imbalance-aware methods obtained successful result in similar contexts, such as in protein function [23, 24] and gene expression [25] prediction, and drug repositioning [26].

By extending a recent network-based approach for detecting disease-gene association which specifically handles the label imbalance [27], the present work proposes an alternative way for coping with the lack of positive instances, based on an efficient procedure for selecting negative examples. After a projection of nodes in the network onto a bidimensional space, positive nodes are clustered using a dynamic version of the fuzzy c-means algorithm (FCM) [28], exploiting a suitable index [29] in order to decide the optimal number of clusters to summarize data. Then, every negative point (corresponding to a gene currently not associated with the studied disease) is assigned a score consisting in its maximum membership to the detected clusters of positive nodes. Such score represents a sort of reliability degree of the negative examples: the higher the membership, the less reliable the node is considered as negative example. We propose here two modalities for embedding the obtained score in the learning model: the first one uses the memberships of negative nodes to weight them during the learning procedure, in a

cost-sensitive fashion; the second one discards the negative nodes whose membership is larger than a fixed threshold. Both variants achieve similar results, with the advantage that the latter one, by appropriately selecting the threshold value of memberships, can significantly reduce the computational complexity of the method, while preserving the overall prediction capability.

We experimentally validated our method on a public benchmark data set for GP, including heterogeneous sources of information for almost nine thousands of human genes, and their associations to around 700 Medical Subject Headings (MeSH)¹ human diseases. The obtained results show a noticeable performance boosting with regard to the best benchmark method, due to both cost-sensitive learning and negative selection procedure. In a second experiment, we further applied our method to select novel candidate genes for some selected diseases, which do not mean novel associations, but gives a clue toward possible studies to validate them.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 is devoted to describe both the gene networks and the network integration techniques adopted in the benchmark experimental setting. In Section 3 we formalize the disease-gene prioritization problem, and introduce our proposed methodology; then in Section 4 we assess its effectiveness through a comparison with state-of-the-art methodologies, argue about the contribution of inferred data, and reports novel putative gene-disease associations. Conclusion remarks end the paper.

MATERIALS

The gene network required by our methodology is obtained by retrieving and integrating several heterogeneous data sources about interactions and/or similarities between genes and their products. In particular we follow the benchmark experimental setup described in [1], which is composed of nine human gene networks covering 8449 genes, and describing functional interactions, transcriptional co-expression/regulation and localization, gene expression profiles, genes-chemicals relationships, protein-protein physical and genetic interactions, and Gene Ontology (GO) [30] semantic similarity. Gene-disease benchmark associations regard 708 selected MeSH disease terms, and are downloaded from the Comparative Toxicogenomics Database (CTD) [31]. Such diseases possess 5 to 200 causative genes. A brief description of every gene network is given below.

Functional interaction network – *finet*. This network covers 8441 selected proteins and contains protein-protein functional binary interactions inferred by a naive Bayes classifier, trained by using information coming from expert-curated biological pathways and from other non curated sources, such as gene co-expression and protein domain interaction [32].

Human net – *hnnet*. In [33] the authors construct 21 large-scale genomics and proteomics data sets from four species integrated into a functional gene network. Diverse distinct lines of evidence, spanning human mRNA coexpression, protein–protein interactions, protein complexes, and comparative genomics data sets, in combination with similar lines of evidence from orthologs in yeast, fly, and worm have been considered.

Cancer module network – *cmnet*. Starting from the work of Segal et al. [34], which collects and describes expression profiles in different tumors in terms of the behavior of gene modules, the authors construct a gene-gene network of 8849 genes, in which two genes are connected if they share at least one of the 263 biological and clinical conditions considered in Segal’s work.

Gene chemical network – *gcnet*. A network of 7649 genes constructed on the base of direct and indirect genes-chemicals interactions available at the CTD database.

BioGRID database network – *dbnet*. A network of protein–protein interactions for 8449 proteins based on direct physical and genetic interactions obtained from BioGRID (v. 3.2.96 – January 2013) [35]

BioGRID projected network – *bgnet*. Instead of binary BioGRID interaction, this network is obtained by firstly constructing a bipartite graph by using physical and genetic interactions between the 8449 considered genes and all the human genes available in BioGRID. Then, a network involving solely the considered genes is built by inserting an edge between two genes if they share at least one neighbour in the bipartite graph.

Semantic similarity networks – *{bp,mf,cc}net*. Three networks obtained by considering the GO terms in the three branches (biological process, molecular function and cellular component) annotating the considered genes. For each branch separately, a network is constructed to consider connected genes which share at least one annotation in the corresponding GO branch. The weight assigned to the edge is the maximum Rensik semantic similarity [36] between all the terms for which the two genes are annotated.

We suspect network *gcnet* may contain a bias toward the predicted MeSH disease terms, since authors did not exclude inferred MeSH gene-disease associations, which already use the interactions between chemicals and genes. In addition, even network *finet* contains some predicted protein-protein interactions; accordingly, we assess the impact of such sources on the whole evaluation process in a dedicated experimental section of the paper.

Network Integration. As mentioned in Section 2, we considered $m = 9$ different networks. In order to deal with the presence of a different number of genes in each network, the union of all genes has been considered. Thus, denoting by n the total number of considered genes, each network is described by a $n \times n$ matrix $\mathbf{W}^{(d)}$, for $d = 1, \dots, m$ and a generic element $\mathbf{W}_{ij}^{(d)} \in [0, 1]$ of

this matrix represents some notion of functional similarity between genes i and j . The above mentioned extension simply consists in filling with zeroes the missing entries in every matrix. As a pre-processing step, in order to remove too small (and noisy) similarities, we deleted smaller edges according to [1], so as to ensure at least one neighbor for each node.

Single networks have been subsequently fused adopting their *unweighted integration*, which in [1] was shown to perform better among a set of other unweighted schemes. It consists in simply averaging the m adjacency matrices of all available networks, i.e. $\mathbf{W}^* = \sum_{d=1}^m \mathbf{W}^{(d)} / m$. The Laplacian normalization is finally applied to the integrated network \mathbf{W}^* obtaining the matrix $\mathbf{W} = \mathcal{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{W}^* \mathcal{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, where \mathcal{D} is a diagonal matrix $\mathcal{D}_{ii} = \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{W}_{ij}^*$.

We performed numerical experiments on two networks, respectively called Net_6 and Net_9 henceforth. The former has been built excluding all the semantic similarity-based networks from the integration process (thus combining a total of six networks). The latter was obtained through unweighted integration of all networks previously described (relying in this case on nine networks).

METHODS

In this section we first introduce a formalization of the problem setting, then we describe the proposed methodologies: the approach adopted in [27] for ranking genes, the score measure of negative samples and how it can be used to both embed the negative selection strategy in the overall process and to drive the cost-sensitive learning algorithm.

PROBLEM SETTING

We model the disease-gene prioritization problem as a semi-supervised bipartite ranking problem on undirected graphs. More precisely, we represent a gene network in terms of an undirected weighted graph $G = (V, \mathbf{W})$, with vertices in the set $V = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ corresponding to genes and edges described by the matrix \mathbf{W} integrating all networks (see the end of previous section). The set of genes is partitioned as $V = S \cup U$, with S and U disjoint subsets. The former gathers instances labeled according to a given MeSH subject heading, thus it is further divided into the sets S_+ and S_- respectively containing positive and negative instances. The latter includes unlabeled instances, thus representing the object of our inference.

The *disease-gene prioritization* (GP) problem consists therefore in learning how to rank unlabeled genes according to a function $\phi : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, by assigning to future positive instances higher values rather than to negative ones. Summing up, GP is cast as a semi-supervised learning problem on graphs, since the above ranking can be inferred exploiting the information provided by labeled and unlabeled nodes (genes), as well as by the connections linking them.

Moreover, the complexity of the problem under study is also affected by a strong imbalance between negatively and positively labeled nodes in the graphs under investigation, which present a strong disproportion in favour of the former, that is $|S_+|/|S_-| \ll 1$.

COST-SENSITIVE ALGORITHM FOR GP

The bipartite ranking problem introduced in Section 3.1 has been solved relying on a generalized linear model (GLM) with the following properties:

- its predictors are chosen exploiting the similarities between nodes as encoded in the weight matrix W ;
- the sign of its response variable decides whether the membership should be decreed to positive or negative class.

In order to extract meaningful information exploiting the network topology to be fed to the GLM as input, we consider the following two features². That is, each node $i \in S$ is associated with the point $\Delta_i = (\Delta_i^+, \Delta_i^-)$ in the plane (see Figure 1(a)), whose coordinates are

$$\Delta_i^+ = \sum_{j \in S_+} w_{ij} \tag{1}$$

$$\Delta_i^- = \sum_{j \in S_-} w_{ij} \tag{2}$$

It is easy to see that the more a node i exhibits a functional similarity with regard to positive nodes, the higher the value of the corresponding coordinate Δ_i^+ . Analogously for negative nodes, when considering the second coordinate Δ_i^- . Recalling the fact that there is a bijective correspondence between genes and vertices in the graph, this projection is likely to identify a bipartition of S in which (i) positive nodes will tend to concentrate in the lower-right region of the first quadrant, and (ii) negative nodes will distribute in the rest of the same quadrant. This mapping has the following distinctive features:

- the projected space only has two dimensions, therefore it lets us avoid the *curse of dimensionality* problem;
- the projected positive and negative images of nodes can be associated with different misclassification costs during the learning algorithm for the GLM model, thus giving us a first tool to address the class imbalance problem.

We adopted the four GLM models described in the following list.

LR – Linear regression model. While it has become increasingly common habit to disregard such technique in case of dichotomous categorical dependent variables, mainly to avoid the risk of "impossible predictions" (i.e. results outside of the unit interval), we decided to include it in our analysis in view of both the straightforward

Figure 1: A visualization of the proposed methodology workflow.

interpretability of its coefficients, the not negligible speed-up factor observed when large datasets are given in input to the model, and, following argumentations in [37], the groundlessness of the aforementioned risks when interactions terms are included in the model.

LogR – Logit regression model. Together with *probit* model, it is one of the widely used regression models for binary response variables. Despite the different assumptions the two models make about the error distribution (standard logistic the former, and normal distribution for the latter), results tend to be so similar that preference for one over the other model varies by discipline. We opted to work with logistic regression (whose link function reads as $g(x) = \log(x/(1-x))$, with x independent variable) mainly for the straightforward interpretation of the estimated coefficients [38].

CLogLR – Cloglog regression model. While logit and probit are symmetric link functions (they approach 0 at the same rate as they approach 1), the choice of a skewed link function should provide a better fit to unbalanced data [39]. Binomial regression model with complementary log-log link function (defined as $g(x) = \log(-\log(1-x))$) is frequently used when the probability of an event is very small, i.e. when the observed data is not symmetric in the unit interval, increasing slowly at small to moderate value, then sharply near 1.

PR – Poisson regression model. As an alternative to an asymmetric link function, the choice of a discrete and skewed distribution for the response variable is often suggested [40]. Poisson regression with the canonical log link function, introduced to model count, rate, or time-to-events data, is widely used also in case of binary outcome variables to cope with rare events. Indeed, imbalance classification problems represent a typical scenario to apply Poisson regression, since the main assumption the model relies on, that is the expected value and variance of the response variable coincide, is always (at least approximately) satisfied.

Among the various cost-sensitive extensions enabling regression learning algorithms to deal with the class imbalance problems (the interested reader can refer for instance to [41]), we adopted *maximum weighted likelihood estimation* [42]. This scheme consists in maximizing the sum of sample items' log-densities (suitably weighted using a coefficient $\omega \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$, directly linked to the influence of a sample point in the overall optimization process). More precisely, we propose two weighting schemes to be applied to the above vanilla regression models. Letting n_+ and n_- respectively denote the number of positive and negative instances, each scheme is identified by the weight vectors ω^a and ω^b , whose components are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_i^a &= \begin{cases} 1/n_+ & \text{if gene } i \in S_+ \\ 1/n_- & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \omega_i^b &= \begin{cases} \Delta_i^+ / \sum_{j \in S_+} \Delta_j^+ & \text{if gene } i \in S_+ \\ 1/n_- & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Intuitively, both schemes give a higher weight to infrequent instances in the hope of compensating the class imbalance. Moreover, the second scheme adopts a higher variability of positive weights, giving a larger influence to positive nodes exhibiting a higher similarity with nodes belonging to the same class. Thus, the bigger is the positive neighborhood of a positive node, the higher will be its influence in the overall maximization process. Finally, the learned model provides the function ϕ described in Section 3.1 to rank genes in U .

Considering all possible combinations of GLMs and weight schemes, we obtained a total of 12 models. We will distinguish among them using the name convention "[W]GP-*mod* [ws]" (in which square brackets are used to denote optional arguments), where:

- GP and WGP stands for Gene Prioritization and Weighted Gene Prioritization, respectively,
- *mod* is an acronym denoting one of the GLMs,
- *ws* $\in \{ 'a', 'b' \}$ selects one of the two weighting schemes in (3).

SELECTION OF NEGATIVE EXAMPLES

Let $D = \{\Delta_i | i \in S\}$, $D_+ = \{\Delta_i | i \in S_+\}$ and $D_- = \{\Delta_i | i \in S_-\}$ be, respectively, the sets of

projected, positive and negative points. Following [43], the negative selection procedure consists in scoring points in D_- according to their relation with regard to a fuzzy clustering of the set D_+ of positive points. The clustering is the result of an iterated fuzzy c-means (FCM) algorithm [28], modifying at each time the number of clusters with the aim of optimizing the corresponding *fuzzy silhouette* index [29] (an extension of the original, crisp silhouette index [44] which was conceived precisely in order to account for the fuzzy nature of the membership to the clusters in output of the FCM algorithm).

When the iterated procedure ends, we rank each point $\Delta \in D_-$ according to its maximum membership to the c found clusters (Figure 1(b)), that is

$$\sigma(\Delta) = \max_{1 \leq k \leq c} \left\{ \frac{1}{d(\Delta, v_k)^{\frac{2}{\alpha-1}}} \right\} \left(\sum_{j=1}^c \frac{1}{d(\Delta, v_j)^{\frac{2}{\alpha-1}}} \right)^{-1}, \quad (4)$$

where v_1, \dots, v_c are the cluster centroids, and d denotes the distance function used by the FCM algorithm (in Section 4.2 we tested different choices for d , namely the Euclidean, Manhattan, L3, L5, and L7 distances). Finally, α is a free fuzzification parameter: the experiments in Section 4 were conducted by setting $\alpha = 2$, as is common practice when running the FCM algorithm; we also tested slightly different values for this parameter, obtaining negligible variations in the results. We did not explore higher values of α because the resulting σ would be of limited use. This is shown in Figure 2, illustrating heatmaps of σ values for a clustering obtained processing bidimensional points randomly drawn from a mix of three gaussian distributions. More precisely, each map in the figure corresponds to a choice for α (in $\{2, 2.5, 4\}$) and d (between the Euclidean and the Manhattan distances). A darker shade corresponds to higher values of σ , thus highlighting that the resulting ranking has a variance rapidly decreasing when α increases³. Therefore, high values of α lead in our case to less expressive rankings, due to the fact that for high α memberships tend to become indistinguishable.

The obtained score has been used to modify the second weighting scheme in (3): namely, for $i \notin S_+$

$$\omega_i^b = 1 - \sigma(\Delta_i), \quad (5)$$

in the idea that a low value of σ tends to identify points not reasonably belonging to any clusterization of positive instances. Such points will thus be considered as good representatives for the negative class, and assigned a larger weight in the learning process.

We underline that this part of the proposed methodology is appealing also in terms of computational complexity: indeed, the projected space dimension is fixed to 2, thus each run of the repeated FCM algorithm will require $\mathcal{O}(Ic^2|S_+|)$ steps, denoting by I the number

Figure 2: Dependency of score results on clustering distance d and fuzzyfication parameter α . Black and red bullets show respectively the original points (in the (Δ^+, Δ^-) Euclidean reference system) and the obtained cluster centroids.

of iterations in one run of the clustering algorithm. Note that c is *a fortiori* lower than the number of positives, which in turn is very small in our context. As for the ranking of each point, the distance d of 2-feature vectors is computed in $\mathcal{O}(1)$ time and the time complexity of computing $\sigma(\Delta) \forall \Delta \in D_-$ is $\mathcal{O}(|D_-|)$, since $c \leq |S_+|$ and $|S_+|/|S_-| \ll 1$. Thus, the overall complexity of the procedure computing weights to be used in order to rank the examples is $\mathcal{O}(Ic^2|S_+| + |D_-|)$.

A MODEL VARIANT

The score σ in (4) can also be used in order to perform a negative selection procedure aimed at correcting the label imbalance in the available data. More precisely, a subset $\bar{D}_- \subseteq D_-$ of representative negative points can suitably be selected in order to feed the cost-sensitive methods of Section 3.2 a reduced training set $D_+ \cup \bar{D}_-$. The selection procedure is based on the observation that a non-positive point ranked below a suitably fixed threshold $\tau > 0$ cannot be reasonably attributed to any cluster of positive points, whereas nodes corresponding to points $D_{-, \tau} = \{\Delta \in D_- | \sigma(\Delta) \geq \tau\}$ are the ones to be filtered out before further processing (Figure 1(c)). We highlight that such filtering process, despite adding a new parameter (the threshold τ), can significantly lower the ranking complexity obtained at the end of Section 3.3 by diminishing the value of $|D_-|$. Summing up, this variant of the proposed model is depicted in Figure 1: instances are projected onto a bidimensional space (Figure 1(a)); negative instances are ranked according to a clusterization of positive examples (Figure 1(b)); a selection procedure is operated on negative examples (Figure 1(c)); and finally a GLM is learned to separate the retained projected

points using the weighting scheme (5) (Figure 1(d))⁴.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section we first describe the results of the comparison between the state-of-the-art methodologies and methods described in Section 3.2, then we show the results of their extensions based on negative selection procedures presented in Sections 3.3 and 3.4.

STATE-OF-THE-ART-COMPARISON

The state-of-the-art benchmark methods adopted in [1] are briefly describe below.

Kernelized score functions. It is a kernel-based ranking method which extends the similarity between two nodes i and j also to non neighboring nodes by exploiting a suitable kernel matrix [1]. Given a disease M and a gene i , the score is defined according to an appropriate 'distance' $d(i, V_M)$ exploiting in turn the distance, in a suitably chosen Hilbert space, between i and the subset of genes $V_M \subset V$ associated with M . According to the definition of $d(i, V_M)$, authors obtained different scoring methods:

- S_{NN} , when $d(i, V_M)$ is the minimum distance (in \mathcal{H}) between i and V_M (precisely between the images in \mathcal{H} of i and V_M),
- S_{kNN} , when $d(i, V_M)$ is defined by considering just the closest k neighbours in V_M ,
- S_{AV} , when $d(i, V_M)$ is defined as the average distance between i and V_M .

Method	AUC	Method	AUC	Method	AUC
WGP-CLogLR b	0.8777	RWR $\theta = 0.6$	0.8565	$S_{kNN} t = 1, k = 19$	0.8138
WGP-LogR b	0.8767	GP-PR	0.8563	RW $t = 3$	0.7937
WGP-CLogLR a	0.8762	$S_{AV} t = 2$	0.8562	RW $t = 5$	0.7773
WGP-LR b	0.8757	$S_{AV} t = 10$	0.8548	RW $t = 10$	0.7720
WGP-LR a	0.8748	$S_{AV} t = 1$	0.8538	$S_{kNN} t = 10, k = 3$	0.7636
WGP-LogR a	0.8737	RWR $\theta = 0.6$	0.8533	$S_{kNN} t = 5, k = 3$	0.7405
GP-LR	0.8705	$S_{kNN} t = 10, k = 19$	0.8374	$S_{kNN} t = 3, k = 3$	0.7332
WGP-PR a	0.8680	GP-CLogLR	0.8365	$S_{kNN} t = 2, k = 3$	0.7304
WGP-PR b	0.8665	GBA	0.8313	$S_{kNN} t = 1, k = 3$	0.7280
GP-LogR	0.8648	$S_{kNN} t = 5, k = 19$	0.8251	$S_{NN} t = 10$	0.7251
$S_{AV} t = 5$	0.8596	$S_{kNN} t = 3, k = 19$	0.8199	$S_{NN} t = 5$	0.7020
$S_{AV} t = 3$	0.8580	RW $t = 2$	0.8186	$S_{NN} t = 3$	0.6968
RW $t = 1$	0.8566	$S_{kNN} t = 2, k = 19$	0.8170	$S_{NN} t = 2$	0.6950
				$S_{NN} t = 1$	0.6934

Table 1: Average AUC across MeSH terms on the network Net6.

As kernel matrix the t -step ($t = 1, 2, \dots$) random walk kernel K^t is adopted, where $K = \gamma I + \mathcal{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} W \mathcal{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, I is the $n \times n$ identity matrix, and $\gamma > 0$, where \mathcal{D} is again the diagonal degree matrix of W .

Random walks. It is the t -step random walk (RW) algorithm [45], in which the score assigned to a node $i \in V$ is the probability that a t -steps random walk in the graph, starting from positive nodes (in our setting, nodes associated with the disease) ends at node i . The transition matrix of the random walker is obtained from W by row normalization.

Random walks with restart. The random walk with restart (RWR) algorithm is based on the observation that after many steps the walker may forget the prior information coded in the initial probability vector for a MeSH term M (0 for nodes in $V \setminus V_M$ and $1/|V_M|$ for nodes in V_M). Here \setminus is the set complement. Indeed, the walker is allowed to move another random walk step with probability $1 - \theta$, or to restart from its initial condition with probability θ .

Guilt-by-association methods. Algorithms which rely upon the guilt-by-association (GBA) rule make predictions based on the interacting genes, assuming that interacting genes are likely to share similar functions [46, 47]. Usually, the discriminant score for a gene i with regard to a given disease M is obtained as sum of the weights connecting i to neighbouring genes associated with the disease M , or as the maximum of these weights. The benchmark results adopts the latter version.

Generalization capabilities of the methods have been estimated by averaging the performances observed through the classical k -fold cross-validation (CV), with $k = 5$. Performances have been assessed using both the *Area Under the ROC Curve* (AUC) and the *Precision at different Recall levels* (PXR).

Following the benchmark setting, we first run GLM methods on the network Net6 (see Section 2). Table 1 reports the average AUC obtained, sorted in decreasing order. GLM methods (except for

GP-PR and GP-CLogLR) achieve better results than the top-performing benchmark algorithm ($S_{AV} t = 5$). This improvement outlines both the informativeness of the features obtained by node projection (Equations (1-2)), and the effectiveness of the cost-sensitive GLM model to cope with the label imbalance. In particular, to verify the benefit introduced by the cost-sensitive strategy, we show in Figure 3 the paired AUC obtained by vanilla regression and the corresponding cost-sensitive 'b' version for cloglog and logit link functions (similar trends were obtained for all other paired comparisons – results not shown).

It is immediate to observe a large majority of bullets lying above the bisector, showing that cost-sensitive variants achieve higher AUC values for most of the considered diseases.

Indeed, in the first two columns of Table 2 we report the proportion of MeSH terms where cost-sensitive methods outperform the corresponding vanilla ones. Such proportion ranges from 70.1% to 85.9%.

	Network Net6		Network Net9	
	WGP a	WGP b	WGP a	WGP b
GP-LR	0.701	0.709	0.688	0.756
GP-LogR	0.743	0.804	0.441	0.579
GP-CLogLR	0.833	0.859	0.610	0.638
GP-PR	0.768	0.732	0.513	0.535

Table 2: Proportion of wins (in terms of AUC) of cost-sensitive vs. cost-insensitive methods, observed over all the considered diseases.

To statistically assess the significance of such results, we performed the one-sided Wilcoxon Signed Rank test between all couples of methods within the same family (vanilla GLM and the weighted variants 'a' and 'b'). Both cost-sensitive models show meaningful improvements with regard to their vanilla version (p -value < 0.001), while 'b' scheme significantly outperforms the 'a' variant – confirming our initial assumption that positives, carrying more information than negatives, should be

Figure 3: Paired AUC comparison on *Net6* between cost-sensitive scheme 'b' and the corresponding vanilla version for GP algorithm with (a) cloglog and (b) logit link functions.

Method	AUC	Method	AUC	Method	AUC
WGP-CLogLR b	0.8897	GP-PR	0.8877	$S_{kNN} t = 5, k = 19$	0.8500
WGP-LR b	0.8895	GP-LR	0.8860	$S_{kNN} t = 3, k = 19$	0.8413
WGP-CLogLR a	0.8894	$S_{AV} t = 5$	0.8831	$S_{kNN} t = 2, k = 19$	0.8368
WGP-LogR b	0.8890	GP-CLogLR	0.8827	$S_{kNN} t = 1, k = 19$	0.8322
WGP-LR a	0.8889	$S_{AV} t = 3$	0.8811	$S_{NN} t = 10$	0.7437
GP-LogR	0.8889	$S_{AV} t = 2$	0.8792	$S_{NN} t = 5$	0.7106
WGP-PR b	0.8884	$S_{AV} t = 1$	0.8765	$S_{NN} t = 3$	0.7014
WGP-PR a	0.8884	$S_{AV} t = 10$	0.8761	$S_{NN} t = 2$	0.698
WGP-LogR a	0.8881	$S_{kNN} t = 10, k = 19$	0.8665	$S_{NN} t = 1$	0.695

Table 3: Average AUC across MeSH terms on the network *Net9*.

taken into account when learning the predictive model. Nevertheless, such trend breaks down in linear and Poisson regressions, where scheme 'a' is significantly better than variant 'b' (p -value = 0.025). We conjecture that such results are due to the convergence of GLM fitting procedures toward spurious optima in rare instances which, in turn, may be caused by the peaked landscape of weights distribution in 'b' scheme.

Finally, from a time complexity standpoint, GLM method takes around 5 seconds to perform the entire 5-fold CV procedure for a single MeSH disease term on an Intel i7-860 CPU 2.80 GHz machine with 16 GB of RAM, showing good scalability properties, which derive from fast convergence of regression performed in the 2-dimensional projected space.

Similar trends are obtained when running the proposed methods over the network *Net9*, as shown in Table 3. Results obtained by GBA, RW and RWR methods are not reported in the referenced papers due to their low performances. Again, all our methods (except for GP-CLogLR) outperform the best benchmark method ($S_{AV} t = 5$). It is worth noting that GP-CLogLR b, the top method, has a noticeable gain with reference to the correspondent vanilla version, which ranks at thirteenth place.

The Wilcoxon Signed Rank test confirms the results observed for the network *Net6*, with some exceptions. There are no meaningful differences between both the

two cost-sensitive variants of the Poisson model, and between the 'a' scheme and its vanilla version (p -value > 0.05). Furthermore, the logistic regression is the only model privileging the vanilla variant with regard to the corresponding 'a' schema (p -value < 0.001). The exceptional nature of such an event is confirmed by the entries reported in the last two columns of Table 2: although we observe a lower proportion (comparing with network *Net6*) of wins of weighted schemes over their cost-insensitive variants, six out of eight entries still show a remarkable disproportion in favor of weighted schemes.

As further investigation, in Figure 4 we report the box-and-whiskers plot of all proposed methods, which allows to get novel insights about the AUC distributions over diseases.

Boxes are colored so as to reflect the ranking of the methods, obtained by performing all pairwise comparisons under the one-sided Wilcoxon Signed Rank test. Models sharing the same color represent maximal sets of indistinguishable methods under the above test with 0.05 significance level. In particular, all methods ranking fourth downward are joined together in the same class, for the sake of visualization. In addition to the already discussed improvements of weighted schemes, we can appreciate a smaller variance and a reduced presence of outliers (not shown in the pictures), together with a marked skewness toward lower AUC

Figure 4: Performance distribution of the proposed methods across MeSH terms for: (a) network *Net6*, and (b) network *Net9*. Box colors depict the performance ranking of each method, the darker the color, the worst the ranking. In such setting, boxes sharing the same colors represent indistinguishable methods.

Figure 5: PXR levels achieved by benchmark methods on the network *Net6* (a) and *Net9* (b).

values. This is confirmed by the fact that means of AUC distributions (black markers in the pictures) are always lower than their medians (depicted with notches).

Evaluating performances through means, as done in Tables 1 and 3, strongly penalizes all methods, being mean values strongly affected by the presence of outliers having low AUC values. To guarantee a fair comparison with benchmark results, we still make use of such estimator, noting that median values give a more informative and less biased view of the overall performances.

This first experiment ends with the analysis of the PXR results for recall levels ranging from 0.1 to 1, with steps of 0.1 (Figure 5). The performances of the proposed GP methods are very close one another, and for this reason we report just the results for vanilla and cost-sensitive 'b' scheme methods. To better appreciate the advantage of working with cost-sensitive methods, we use a circle shape for all vanilla methods, and square shape for their cost-sensitive variants. We observe a remarkable improvement with regard to $S_{AV} t = 2$ (triangles in the

figure), the only method of which authors published the PXR performances, except for the precision value at 0.1 recall level in picture (b); whereas the gain of weighted schemes compared to vanilla versions are slight but however non trivial.

Moreover, in Fig. 5(a) we note how vanilla methods tend to be more accurate for lower levels of recall. Nevertheless, for all the remaining recall values, in particular in the range [0.3, 1], cost-sensitive methods always outperform vanilla ones.

EVALUATION OF NEGATIVE SELECTION CONTRIBUTION

This section is dedicated to investigate the contribution given by the negative selection procedure proposed in Sections 3.3 and 3.4. We consider the top method in the experimental comparison carried out in Section 4.1, namely *WGP-ClogLR b* (*WGP-ClogLR* in short), and extend it by embedding our negative selection strategy. We name this algorithm *NWGP EUCL*, *NWGP MANH*, *NWGP LX*, respectively when

Figure 6: AUPRC values averaged across diseases on Net6 and Net9.

using Euclidean, Manhattan and LX $\{X = 3, 5, 7\}$ distances. To better analyze the behaviour of our method, we also consider the Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUPRC) as performance metric, in addition to the metrics already adopted in the benchmark setting, since AUPRC is more informative than AUC on unbalanced settings [48].

In Figure 6 the average AUPRC values are reported, while in Figure 7 we show the obtained precision at different recall levels. AUC values achieved by NWGP methods are almost indistinguishable, with maximum value 0.8990 for NWGP L5, which outperforms WGP-ClogLR (AUC value = 0.8897).

Even the results in terms of AUPRC show that methods which adopt the negative selection strategy have a statistically significant improvement over WGP-ClogLR on both Net6 and Net9 (Wilcoxon signed rank test, p -value < 0.001). Since our method has almost indistinguishable performance when adopting different distances in the projected space, from now on we will refer to the Euclidean one.

In order to better investigate the behavior of our method, we tested on the most informative network (Net9) the variant in which after determining the empirical distribution of the fuzzy memberships to clusters made by positives (Equation (4)), we filter out the negatives whose membership value is above a threshold τ (see Section 3.4). Here τ is set as the k -quantile of the empirical distribution of the memberships, with $k \in \{0.05, 0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75\}$. The results are reported in Figure 8 together with the corresponding time in seconds for computing the entire cycle of cross validation on a single MeSH term. Interestingly, when discarding respectively $\{75, 50, 25\}$ % of negatives, the performances of the model are almost identical. On the other side, the execution time increases with τ . Only for $k < 0.2$ both AUC and AUPRC significantly drop. From these results it seems that the best compromise would be $0.20 < k < 0.5$, but we suggest an appropriate learning step, where k (and consequently τ) is tuned on a small subset of training data, for example through

hold-out or cross-validation procedures.

CONTRIBUTION OF INFERRED DATA

As we mentioned in Section 2, input networks *gcnet* and *finet* contain inferred protein-protein associations, and this may introduce a bias in the overall procedure. In particular, *gcnet* contains gene-chemical relationships, directly observed or inferred (that is when a chemical is related to a protein via intermediate events), and benchmark gene-disease associations include also inferred associations, which in turn are obtained by exploiting curated gene-chemical interactions: a gene i is associated with disease d because gene i has a curated interaction with chemical c , and chemical c has a curated association with disease d . The associations between genes and diseases adopted in the benchmark have thereby exploited some *gcnet* interactions, thus introducing a bias.

To assess to which extent this affected the final results, we performed a further experiment where network *gcnet* has been excluded from the input data (No.*gcnet* network). Furthermore, even *finet* network includes protein-protein interactions inferred by a classifier trained on curated protein-protein interactions. Unlike *gcnet*, this is not a bias toward gene-disease associations, but simply means that some connections are putative. To evaluate the relevance of these putative protein-protein interactions, we performed another experiment excluding just *finet* from the input networks (No.*finet* network).

Finally, we also tested our methodology on a network integrating all but *gcnet* and *finet* networks (No.*inferred* network). In all the novel experiments we tested the method NWGP: the related results are shown in Figure 9. AUC and AUPRC differences show a similar trend, with larger AUPRC differences. On the No.*finet* integrated network we notice a reduced performance deterioration (-0.0033 (0.4%) AUC and -0.0152 (7.8%) AUPRC) compared to the results on Net9, suggesting that protein interactions added through a supervised classifier just slightly impact on the overall performance (*finet* data also contain curated interactions, whose removal participates in the shown deterioration). It is significant that even without network *finet* the average AUC (0.895) is still larger than the top benchmark method (0.8831) using all the input data. Removing the *gcnet* network causes instead a much higher performance decay in both AUC (-0.0447 (4.98%)) and AUPRC (-0.0641 (33.3%)), and this is not surprising, since, as stated above, the *gcnet* network partially contains information about gene-disease associations. Nevertheless, such a result of course does not invalidate the conclusions of the overall benchmark comparison and the assessment of the negative selection contribution (which are the main goals of this work), since all methods have been compared on the same data and adopting the same setting.

Figure 7: PXR levels averaged across diseases on *Net6* (a) and *Net9* (b) achieved by methods embedding negative selection procedure.

Disease name	MeSH ID	# genes	Candidate genes
Vanishing White Matter with Ovarian Failure	C565836	5	EIF2S1, AKT1, EIF2S2
Peroxisome biogenesis disorders	C536664	10	PEX5, NOX3, PEX7
Epidermolysis Bullosa, Junctional, Non-Herlitz Type	C562639	5	NID1, ODZ2, COL4A5
Maple Syrup Urine Disease	D008375	5	DHTKD1, WARS2, ATP5B
Coffin-Siris syndrome	C536436	6	SMARCC1, SMARCD1, SMARCC2
Upper Extremity Deep Vein Thrombosis	D056824	15	PLAT, F11, INHBE

Table 4: Diseases and genes selected for candidate novel gene–disease associations.

SELECTING NOVEL CANDIDATES FOR MeSH DISEASE TERMS

In this section we performed another experiment to select among negative genes few meaningful candidates to be associated with a subset of selected diseases. In particular we chose the top predicted diseases according to the AUPRC value obtained through the cross validation procedure. In order to robustly select the top diseases, we ran the experiment in multiple and different settings: {5,3,2}-fold CV and holdout with 30% data for training and 70% for testing (for achieving more reliable results, the last experiment was iterated 3 times for each term by considering the average performance). This ensures that a selected disease is accurately predicted in different settings, with different amount of training data: 80%, 66.6%, 50% and 30%. We considered the intersection of diseases in the top 50 of each experiment, obtaining a set of 26 diseases. In order to consider diseases as much specific as possible, we then selected those with at most 15 associated genes, obtaining the final set represented

in Table 4, together with the top ranked negative genes in each disease. To understand whether such results make sense from a bio-medical standpoint, we searched for information about the selected diseases, and we found that they do not have novel annotations in the current CTD database (05.10.2016), except for *Peroxisome biogenesis disorders* which has one novel gene associated with (not in the list we suggested). Nevertheless, we found that most candidate genes we reported are associated with the corresponding parent terms in the MeSH hierarchy (with different levels of evidence). Specifically, just citing some in the CTD database, genes AKT1 and EIF2S1 are associated with *Leukoencephalopathies* (respectively with scores 61.58, 26.79 and references 105, 13), parent of *Vanishing White Matter Leukodystrophy with Ovarian Failure*; genes SMARCC1 and SMARCD1 are both associated with *Intellectual Disability* and *Micrognathism* diseases, parents of *Coffin-Siris syndrome*, although with lower evidence ((15.99, 3) and (1.85, 1) for SMARCC1, (3.43, 2) and (2.17, 1) for SMARCD1); finally, genes

Figure 8: AUC, AUPRC averaged over MeSH disease terms and per-term time in seconds when varying the τ parameter, expressed as k -quantile of the membership empirical distribution.

Figure 9: Difference between results obtained by method *NWGP L3* on networks *No.gcnet*, *No.finet*, *No.inferred* and results on network *Net9*. Values show the average difference in terms of AUC and AUPRC.

PLAT (67.66, 129) and *INHBE* (29.20, 32) are currently associated with *Venous Thrombosis* term, parent of *Upper Extremity Deep Vein Thrombosis* disease in the MeSH hierarchy.

On the one hand, information reported in Table 4 do not imply novel gene-disease associations, but simply putative associations that must be appropriately verified. On the other hand, the lack of direct associations in the current databases may depend on the inherent difficulties characterizing the process of manual annotation by individual curators. Indeed, independently of the curator expertise, curation is a laborious task requiring to spend a significant amount of time on reading through papers and trying to locate material that might contain curatable facts, and the final assessment may remain suggestive. Accordingly, different curators, even when following the same annotation policy, may determine different assessments/annotations. Moreover, quite often there is no direct matching between diseases across databases. For example, the CTD disease term *Micrognathism* is not directly present in the OMIM database, but it is instead related to four other OMIM terms: *Hypoglossia-hypodactyly*, (103300), *Joubert syndrome 18* (614815), *Acheiropody* (216340), and *Yunis-Varon syndrome* (216340). In the CTD taxonomy, *Hypoglossia-Hypodactylia* (C566308) is a

sibling term of *Micrognathism*, *Joubert syndrome 18* is not present (only *Joubert syndrome 1* and *10* can be found, which have just the general term *Congenital, Hereditary, and Neonatal Diseases and Abnormalities*, D009358, as common ancestor), *Acheiropody* corresponds to CTD term *Acheiropodia* (C536014), having just one common ancestor with *Micrognathism* term (*Musculoskeletal Abnormalities*, D009139), whereas *Yunis Varon syndrome* (C536719) is a child of *Micrognathism* term. Hence, the annotation of a gene with a parent or a child disease term in a disease hierarchy is affected both by curators' personal discernment and partial absence of direct disease correspondence among medical databases.

CONCLUSIONS

Disease-gene prioritization, the process aiming at finding the genetic cause underlying human disorders, from a computational standpoint is affected by lack of known causative genes for most diseases. Here we have shown that this problem can be effectively handled by adopting computational methodologies which specifically take into account the disproportion between causative (positive) and non causative (negative) genes. Furthermore, the adoption of a procedure to select meaningful negative genes can significantly boost performance of generalized linear regression model in ranking genes according to given diseases. We have also provided a list of possible novel gene-disease associations, along with a fair comparison of the proposed methodology with the state-of-the-art methods for gene prioritization.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS

CTD: Comparative Toxicogenomics Database

FCM: Fuzzy C-Means

GBA: Guilt-By-Association

GCB: Genomics and Computational Biology

GLM: Generalized Linear Model

GP: Gene Prioritization

GO: Gene Ontology

GWAS: Genome Wide Associations Studies

MeSH: Medical Subject Headings

RW: Random Walk

RWR: Random Walk with Restart

SNP: Single Nucleotide Polymorphism

WES: Whole Genome Sequencing

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NOTES

¹<http://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh>

²the number of predictors, actually including a two-way interaction term (i.e. the product of the two features), is equal to 3.

³we also performed a similar experiment for the L_3 , L_5 , and L_7 distances, obtaining results basically identical to those corresponding to Euclidean distance.

⁴we point out that the step depicted in Figure 1(d) is common to all the model variants.